

**SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER AT
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS:
PRACTICAL EXPERIENCE AND SUGGESTIONS FOR
DEVELOPMENT DIRECTIONS**

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ABSTRACT

In the context of deep international integration and the explosion of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, scientific research (SR) and technology transfer (TT) play an essential role in promoting sustainable socio-economic development. Research institutions affiliated with educational institutions are not only places for training high-quality human resources but also centers for innovation, technology application, efficient resource exploitation, and environmental protection. This article presents practical experiences in implementing SR and TT, including defining research objectives linked to practical needs, ensuring the novelty of products, strengthening multilateral cooperation (among S&T units, with businesses, and with local authorities), organizing scientific conferences, and especially promoting the training of research personnel. Existing challenges such as funding issues, administrative hurdles, and the gap between academic research and practical needs are also analyzed. Based on this, the article proposes strategic solutions such as strengthening connections with domestic and international funding bodies, developing strong research groups, promoting tripartite cooperation, and fostering intellectual property registration, to enhance the effectiveness and sustainability of SR and TT, contributing to the development of the institution and the country.

Keywords: *Scientific research, technology transfer, educational institution, university, cooperation, intellectual property, practical experience, challenges.*

1. Introduction Scientific research (SR) and technology transfer (TT) activities are becoming increasingly crucial in the context of the globalized knowledge economy and the remarkable advancements of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. SR is not only the foundation for the significant progress of knowledge but also a direct driving force for innovation and socio-economic development in every nation. Research institutions, particularly those affiliated with educational institutions, fulfill

a dual role: they are cradles for training high-quality professional human resources and centers for developing innovative technologies that serve management, rational resource exploitation, and sustainable environmental protection. SR is considered a vital factor in enhancing training quality, producing a workforce capable of meeting the increasing demands of society. The work of TT, product development, and research commercialization represents the final stage to fully realize the value of intellectual assets created from SR projects.

Duy Tan University (DTU) serves as a typical example of a training and scientific research unit, with an orientation to become a leading institution in applied training and research. The university has placed special emphasis on SR and TT, undertaking numerous science and technology (S&T) projects at international, national, ministerial, and provincial levels. Successful and effective transfers to local areas include: "Technology for producing water filtration equipment and Biodiesel production equipment," "Research to perfect the structural technology for constructing 42m long prestressed I-beams through application in the construction of Hoa Xuan Bridge, Da Nang," "Research to support the design of sand pile reinforcement for the Nguyen Tri Phuong - Hoa Quy road in Da Nang city," "Research on purifying the gene pool for some precious medicinal plants in Tay Giang district," "Research on methods to eradicate the invasive Morning Glory vine on the Son Tra Peninsula," "Research and preparation of some forms of Duy Tan branded filter bag tea," the "Automatic Cocktail Mixing System," "Research, design, and fabrication of an automatic loom shuttle winder," and eCPR - a 3D simulation technology application for building a CPR training system, which received the Sao Khue Award in 2020. This article synthesizes and analyzes practical experiences in the process of implementing scientific research projects and technology transfer activities, thereby proposing orientations and solutions to optimize the effectiveness of these activities.

2. Experiences in Promoting Scientific Research and Technology Transfer Activities For SR products to be successfully transferred to beneficiary units and have high practical applicability, several key experiences have been drawn:

2.1. Defining Research Objectives and Content Linked to Practical Needs Before proposing an SR project, answering two core questions—"What to research?" and "Who for?"—is essential. To achieve this, a thorough understanding of the objectives, content, and requirements of national and local science and technology programs, as well as relevant regulations, policies, and strategic development orientations, is necessary. This approach allows for the identification of timely and urgent research problems that need to be addressed by the state, local authorities, and businesses within each specific sector.

2.2. Ensuring the Novelty and Applicability of Research Products For a research product to have practical applicability and be effective in transfer, in addition to meeting precise scientific arguments, the product must possess true novelty. This necessitates a detailed and systematic literature review to

ensure topicality and avoid duplication. The resulting product must have certain advantages (superiority, distinction) over similar products that have already been transferred or commercialized, such as in terms of cost, supporting technology, or suitability for the beneficiary unit.

2.3. Strengthening Multilateral Cooperation Close collaboration among relevant entities is the key to the success of S&T projects and subsequent product transfer activities. Forms of cooperation can include:

- Cooperation among Individuals and Science and Technology Units: Collaboration among universities, institutes, centers, and individual scientists contributes to forming an optimal knowledge network, effectively utilizing human resources with ambition and passion for research, and maximizing laboratory capabilities and fabrication/practice workshops. Large tasks can be divided into multiple modules, with each unit undertaking one module to jointly achieve the goal of creating a transferable and commercializable product.
- Cooperation between Science and Technology Units and Businesses/Organizations: Strengthening links with businesses through signing cooperation agreements on human resource training and TT, or conducting research based on business requests (orders). This linkage helps universities understand the demand for high-quality human resources and TT from businesses. Businesses act as a lever stimulating innovation, TT, receiving trained products, and providing material and financial resources. Conversely, educational institutions are places where new knowledge is created and solutions for practical, long-standing business problems are sought. This cooperation is a decisive factor for the transferability of project products, as researchers possess deep scientific understanding, while businesses have practical operational knowledge and the conditions to develop products.
- Cooperation among S&T Organizations, Local Authorities, and Businesses: Organizing regular field trips and working sessions allows each party to interact and share their practical needs and core capabilities, thereby identifying suitable cooperation content to be implemented as S&T and TT tasks. Coordination with the Department of Science and Technology is needed to advise local authorities on developing specific mechanisms and policies to leverage the strength, research capabilities, and facilities of educational institutions.

2.4. Organizing Science and Technology Conferences S&T conferences play an important role as a forum for educational institutions, institutes, centers, businesses, and scientists to share their needs and strengths. They are also an occasion for S&T organizations to demonstrate research results and potential applications, while businesses can introduce their products, technologies, and services. This fosters focused discussion and establishes cooperation orientations in SR and TT.

2.5. Promoting the Training and Development of Scientific Research Human Resources The human resources executing S&T projects are a key factor determining the success and quality of the products.

Therefore, S&T organizations need to focus on enhancing the qualifications of their research staff through:

- Organizing training courses on SR methodologies, writing international journal articles, intellectual property, and presentation skills at conferences, to develop comprehensive research skills for young scientists.
- Strengthening collaborative training with foreign universities through co-supervising dissertations and exchanging research students.
- Seeking scholarships and sponsorship programs for young staff to undergo short-term training and research internships abroad.
- Signing cooperation agreements with international research institutes in areas of strength to enhance capacity and standardize research teams.
- Issuing incentive policies to encourage young staff to participate in research, with reward schemes for scientific publications and transferred products.
- Developing clear career development paths for researchers, creating opportunities for advancement based on research achievements.

Proposed model:

3. Challenges and Proposed Solutions Despite achieving many successes, SR and TT activities still face certain challenges:

3.1. Challenges

- Lack of research funding and investment in modern measurement equipment, making it difficult to implement large-scale projects or those requiring high technology.
- Lack of clear and appropriate regulations related to administrative procedures in bidding and TT, leading to delays and complexities in the implementation process.
- The gap between academic research and the practical needs of local authorities/businesses, reducing the applicability and commercialization potential of research results.

3.2. Proposed Solutions To overcome the aforementioned challenges and boost SR activities, the following solutions should be implemented:

- Strengthening connections with national programs and international funding organizations (such as GIZ, KOICA, WB, JICA) to seek funding, while also implementing co-funded programs.
- Developing strong research groups aligned with the strategic direction of the S&T organization and the TT beneficiaries. This helps to concentrate resources and expertise in priority areas.
- Enhancing tripartite cooperation: university – business – local government, to create a more effective ecosystem supporting SR and TT, bridging the gap between theory and practice.
- Promoting intellectual property registration and commercialization of research results, to protect the achievements of creative labor and transform research outcomes into tangible economic value.

4. Conclusion Experience from the implementation process has clearly shown that scientific research and technology transfer activities in many fields at educational institutions only truly become effective when they are correctly oriented and involve close coordination. This includes the linkage between research and practice, between teaching and application, and between the specialized team and the beneficiary community. In the future, the sustainable development of green technologies, increased digital transformation, and international integration will be inevitable trends to enhance research and technology transfer capabilities. These efforts will not only contribute to the sustainable development of the country but also protect environmental resources for future generations.

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